

Common Terms and Definitions; DRAFT - Annex to D2.2 Blueprint

Port operation optimization WP2

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Table of Contents

1	INTRODUCTION	5
1.1	PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT	5
1.2	SCOPE	5
1.3	AUTHORSHIP AND INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPR)	5
1.4	STRUCTURE OF THIS DOCUMENT	6
1.5	RELATIONSHIP WITH OTHER DELIVERABLES	6
1.6	DEFINITIONS AND TERMINOLOGY BASICS	7
1.7	CATEGORISATION OF TERMS	9
2	ABBREVIATIONS	10
3	FOUNDATIONAL TERMS	13
3.1	PROCESSES AND ACTIVITIES	13
3.2	PARTIES AND ROLES	13
3.3	LOCATIONS	14
3.4	EVENTS, STATUS AND MILESTONES	15
3.5	IDENTIFICATION	15
4	GENERAL SUPPLY CHAIN, TRANSPORT AND LOGISTICS TERMS	17
5	SHIP VOYAGE RELATED TERMS	20
5.1	IDENTIFIERS FOR VOYAGE RELATED TERMS	23
6	PORT-TO-PORT PROCESS	24
6.1	IDENTIFIERS FOR PORT PROCESSES	25
7	PARTIES RELATED TO PORT CALLS	26
7.1	IDENTIFICATION OF PARTIES	26
8	ROLES RELATED TO PORT CALLS	27
8.1	IDENTIFICATION OF ROLES RELATED TO THE PORT CALL	29
9	PARTIES RELATED TO THE SHIP AND ITS REPRESENTATIVES	31
10	ROLES RELATED TO THE SHIP AND ITS REPRESENTATIVES	33
11	LOCATIONS	34
11.1	GEOGRAPHIC FEATURES IN PORTS	34
11.1.1	<i>Identifiers for geographic features in ports</i>	36
12	EVENTS, STATUSES AND MILESTONES	38
13	CONTRACTUAL AND REGULATORY TERMS	42
14	INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGY	44
	REFERENCES – STANDARDS – ETCETERA	46
	STANDARDS	46
	REFERENCES	46
	INDEX	50

Figures

FIGURE 1 RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN VOYAGE RELATED TERMS.	22
FIGURE 2 THE PORT CALL COORDINATION CENTRE - IDENTIFICATION OF KEY STAKEHOLDERS	29
FIGURE 3 – THE MOST COMMON SHIP REPRESENTATIVES	31
FIGURE 4 – PORT AREAS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP TO THE ENTIRE PORT AREA	36
FIGURE 5 – VISUALISATION OF THE COMPONENTS OF AN EVENT	41

Tables

TABLE 1- ABBREVIATIONS	10
TABLE 2 – PARTY IDENTIFIERS AND REFERENCE CODES.....	27
TABLE 3 - MAPPING ROLES ACROSS INDUSTRY INITIATIVES	29
TABLE 4 - LOCATION IDENTIFICATION	36

1 Introduction

A common understanding among sometimes large numbers of stakeholders from diverse backgrounds involved in a process that requires coordination and communication, will be a precondition “sine qua non” for successful collaboration their process. This applies throughout supply chains and transport and logistics networks. It most definitely also applies to the collaboration of the DYNAPORT participants to achieve the objectives of the DYNAPORT project.

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document contains terms and definition as well as abbreviations that are used across multiple documents and deliverables produced by the DYNAPORT project. The document will be updated continuously during the DYNAPORT project to meet the needs of the project participants and any parties that are involved in the DYNAPORT project or associated projects.

This document does not in any way aim to be a comprehensive set of terminology for the Maritime mode of transport. Its primary aim is to provide a solid foundation of semantics that will be used consistently across the DYNAPORT project. As such, it is a fundamental building block for achieving Semantic Interoperability in line with the European Interoperability Framework (EIF). [1]

Parts of this may be proposed to various international Standard Development Organisations (SDO)¹ as inputs to the standards development processes of those standardisation organisations. These SDO include, but are not limited to ISO, UN/CEFACT, ASTM, GS1, IHO, ITPCO, BIMCO, DCSA and others.

The document will also, to the extent feasible, use terms and definitions that are already available from standardisation organisations; we will clearly reference the sources of terms and definitions.

1.2 Scope

The scope of these definitions is “Digital interfaces and ICT architecture for communication between ship and shore parties”. This requires some extensions into purely shipping or purely port issues, but the intention is to not make this a general trade or transport definition of terms. All definitions of terminology should be within this defined scope.

1.3 Authorship and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

All content described in this document is in the public domain and may be used freely. This includes terms and definitions that have been sourced from standardisation organisations. This document will be made available through the DYNAPORT project web pages as well as other channels.

¹ Preferably the organisations will comply with the criteria for SDO published by the WTO (see list at <https://tbtcode.iso.org/list-of-standardizing-bodies.html>), but the DYNAPORT results may be used by other organisations and incorporated into their terminology materials. https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/tbt_e/principles_standards_tbt_e.htm

1.4 Structure of this document

The sections are organized as follows:

- This is the introduction and general scope
- Terminology basics
What we need to know before creating terms and definitions?
- Categorisation of Terms
- Chapters for each Category of Terms
- References
This unnumbered section contains references. The corresponding reference in the text is the number in square brackets, e.g. [1].
- Index
This unnumbered section provides an alphabetically sorted list of Keywords with page-numbers where they appear. The Index is intended to simplify finding the appropriate terms and definitions.

1.5 Relationship with other deliverables

The present document is the first version of the deliverable “Common Terms and Definitions” that is part of the deliverables for Work Package 2 (WP2).

The contents of this document have been aligned with the work done for several other deliverables such as D2.1 “Description of port call processes”, D3.1 “Multi-party cooperation and goal alignment for voyage optimization” and D5.1 “Maritime ICT Reference Architecture”.

This document aims to serve several purposes:

- Enable consistent use of terms and definitions across all deliverables and other materials produced by the DYNAPORT project
- Provide the basis for consistent use of terminology with other initiatives focussed on improving maritime and ports processes and how they relate with Supply Chain processes extending into the hinterland. Among those initiatives are the MISSION project and other projects funded by the European Union as well as initiatives that indicated their intent to collaborate as part of the so-called Port Call Optimization (PCO) Network coordination group.
- Provide the basis for contributions and input to the efforts of (global) standards development organisations (SDO) such as ISO, IMO, IHO, UN/CEFACT, GS1 and others that serve the communities in transportation and/or supply chains.

1.6 Definitions and terminology basics

Writing good term and definition combinations is **not** a trivial exercise.

Various standards development organisations (SDO) have spent significant time to develop “rules” or “guides” that must be applied when standard terms & definitions are developed within that SDO.

There are some criteria and recommendations that appear to be common to most of the SDO guidelines:

- **Use plain language**
 - a. Write the definition with the users of the term in mind.
Choose language and verbiage that will convey the meaning of the term effectively to the target audience.
 - b. Be clear and concise but avoid oversimplification. The language used must always convey the meaning accurately.
 - c. Keep sentences short and each sentence should convey a single idea.
- **Avoid ambiguity**
 - a. Terms and definitions must **not** be open to interpretation.
 - b. Add further explanation to a term (not part of the definition, but clearly linked to the term), where that helps the reader to better or correctly understand the meaning and (scope of) application of the term.
- **Include references to authoritative sources**
 - a. A term may build on terms and definitions that already exist. If so, including references to authoritative sources for the existing terms and definitions will help to convey the meaning of the new term correctly.

Within the DYNAPORT project we will use the “Form and Style Guide” [2] for terms and definitions (semantics) from the ASTM standards development organisation.

The ASTM Guide provides the most detailed description of how to implement the above criteria for writing robust terms and definitions². The “American Society for Testing and Materials” (ASTM) organisation started over 125 years ago to assist the American railways environment in developing the standards they needed to flourish³.

For each term defined in this document we include a “part of speech” abbreviation to indicate how the term may be used in speech or text. It will appear immediately after the term separated by a comma and a space.

Within the DYNAPORT context we distinguish the following parts of speech indicators:

- **Noun**, abbreviated as “n”.
- **Verb**, abbreviated as “v”.
- **Adjective**, abbreviated as “adj”.

Nouns and verbs may be used on their own, but an adjective must be used in combination with a term that is a noun or a verb.

² The authors of this document were not aware of a more suitable guide at the time this choice was made

³ An introductory video is available at <https://youtu.be/TnIsBIFUegY>

It is also important to note that within the context of a vocabulary or glossary (like this document) the terms and definitions need to “build on each other”. That means that the vocabulary needs to include a limited number of foundational terms. These terms cover ideas and concepts that can be refined for a multitude of different contexts using modifiers or qualifiers.

For example,

- “Maritime Terminals” are a kind of terminal; maritime makes the more generic term “terminal” more specific in this context.
- A “Terminal” is a “Physical Location”, which means it is derived from (and more specific than) the term “Physical Location”.
- “Physical Location” clearly is a kind of “Location”

From this example we can see that starting from the foundational concept of a Location, we have added three layers of refinement to arrive at “Maritime Terminal”.

This is an extremely powerful mechanism that will be applied throughout this document.

Most of those terms and definitions that are needed within the DYNAPORT project context, exist, but the problem is that at least for a number of them, the definitions for the same term from different sources are different and sometimes even contradictory.

Probably the most common and “confusing” example is the use of the word “shipment” by different parties in supply chains and Transport and logistics. Standards development organisations like UN/CEFACT, GS1, UBL, ASTM define shipment as “an identifiable collection of one or more goods to be transported from the seller to the buyer.” This is also the way this document defines shipment. However, many (or even most) logistics service providers use the word shipment as a synonym for a Transport Order or Transport Booking. Because the collection of goods transported from seller to buyer may be transported on several different Transport Orders during their journey, especially in multi-modal contexts, this causes no end of confusion between the logistic service providers and the beneficial cargo owners (sellers and buyers of the goods).

To avoid confusion regarding the meaning of terms (semantics), we include the terms and definition required to properly understand the DYNAPORT deliverables in this document.

Terminology is always defined in a context. In this document the context is defined by the heading the terminology is placed under. Normally, we assume that the context is known when a term is used so that the term itself does not need to contain the context. Thus, a ship voyage is defined as just “voyage”.

Other DYNAPORT deliverables may provide additional information related to a specific term within the context of that deliverable, but the definitions provided in this document are applicable across all DYNAPORT deliverables.

1.7 Categorisation of Terms

The DYNAPORT project is rather large, and it covers an emerging process in a very wide environment. This document will therefore contain a substantial number of terms and definitions.

Most “paper-based” vocabularies like this one, tend to present the terms and definitions in an alphabetically sorted sequence. Given the number of terms and definition we expect to include, that approach would very likely make it difficult to find the desired term and its definition. The alphabetic sorting also means that terms that are very much related to each other may end up far apart in the document.

To address those challenges of traditional vocabularies, this vocabulary will categorise each of the terms and then present all terms in the same category together in their own section or chapter. Even within each section, the terms may not be presented in alphabetical order. Where it makes sense, this vocabulary will group related terms (regardless of alphabetical ordering), e.g., to discuss closely related terms and make sure that the differences and the relationships among these terms will be correctly and consistently understood by all those that use this vocabulary.

This vocabulary also includes an Index, within which all terms may be found in alphabetical order with reference to the page where the term is defined and discussed in the body of this vocabulary.

2 Abbreviations

The abbreviations are presented here in an alphabetically sorted list, with no categorisation of any kind.

Table 1- Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
AIS	Automatic Identification System
ASM	Application Specific Message
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
AtoN	Aids to Navigation
BCO	Beneficial Cargo Owner
DCS	Data Collection System of the IMO (see below)
DSC	Digital Selective Calling
ECDIS	Electronic Chart Display and Information System
EOSP	End Of Sea Passage
EPIRB	Emergency Position Indicator Radio Beacon
FAOP	Full Away on (sea) Passage
FCFS	First Come First Served
FIFO	First In First Out
GEO	Geostationary Earth Orbit
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HTTP/ HTTPS	Internet hypertext transfer protocol, secure version is HTTPS
HSP	Hydrographic Service Provider
IALA	International Association for Aids to Navigation and Lighthouse Authorities
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission - Standards organisation
IHO	International Hydrographic Office
IMO	International Maritime Organization
IP	Internet Protocol
IRDM	IMO Reference Data Model
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITS	Intelligent Transport System
ISPS	International Ship and Port Facility Security Code.
JIT	Just-in-Time
JIT Arrival	In DYNAPORT related to the process of JIT Arrival of the ship at berth
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
kbps	Kilo-bits per second
LAT lat.	Lowest Astronomical Tide latitude
LEO	Low Earth Orbit

Abbreviation	Meaning
LNO	Local Nautical Operations
LOCODE	UN/LOCODE - Two + three letter code identifying a geographical area
LOA	Length Overall
LPO	Local Port Operations
LSP	Logistic Service Provider
Mbps	Mega-bits per second
MEO	Medium Earth Orbit
MHz	Mega-Hertz (unit of measure for frequency)
MIRA	Maritime ICT reference architecture
MMT-RDM	Multi-Modal Transport Reference Data Model (by UNECE)
MRN	Maritime resource name
MRV	Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (EU and UK)
MSC	Maritime Safety Committee in IMO
MSW	Maritime Single Window
NAVTEX	"Navigational Telex", Low-bandwidth digital messaging service. mainly on medium and high frequency bands.
NM	Nautical Mile
NOR	Notice of readiness
NSP	Nautical service providers
NTM	Nautical traffic manager
NVP	Nautical voyage planning
OPS	On-shore Power Supply (for ships in port)
OT	Operations Technology
P3C	Port Call Coordination Centre
PBP	Pilot Boarding Place
PCO	Port Call Optimization
PCS	Port Community System
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
Ro-Ro	Roll-on Roll-off
S-100	The new hydrographic system for description of electronic charts and chart overlays
SSAS	Ship Security Alert System
SIP	Strategic Implementation Plan (of e-navigation) [23]
SMS	Ship Management Services
SOA	Service Outcome Agreement
SOLAS	IMO Convention on Safety of Life at Sea
SSP	Ship Services Provider
REST	Representational State Transfer architectural style for HTTP and similar systems
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe

Abbreviation	Meaning
UN/CEFACT	United Nations Centre for Trade Facilitation and Electronic Business. A subsidiary of UNECE responsible for UN/EDIFACT and trade facilitation recommendations and electronic business standards.
UN EDIFACT	Messaging standard developed and maintained by UNECE.
UTC	Universal Time Coordinated
VA	Virtual Arrival
VDE	VHF Data Exchange (2-300 kbps sub-channel of VDES)
VDES	VHF Data Exchange System Not yet fully standardized. Will include the existing AIS.
VHF	Very High Frequency – for ships this is approximately 156-174 MHz. Mostly used for voice communication, but DCS, AIS and VDES all use digital channels in this band.
VTS	Vessel Traffic Services
WCO	World Customs Organization
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

3 Foundational terms

3.1 Processes and activities

Process, n - a set of interrelated or interacting activities to achieve one or more specific outcomes.

DISCUSSION— In business process mapping, a process is visualised to understand how work flows from start to finish, identify inefficiencies, and improve overall performance (Based on ISO/IEC/IEEE 12207).

Task, n – action intended to contribute to the achievement of one or more outcomes of a process.

DISCUSSION— Tasks are the building blocks of a process and are often assigned to natural persons (individuals or teams) or organisations (Based on ISO/IEC/IEEE 12207).

Activity, n – a set of cohesive tasks of a process.

DISCUSSION— An “Activity” represents a higher-level action within a process. For example, “preparing a report” could be an activity that includes tasks like gathering data, analysing information, and writing the report (ISO/IEC/IEEE 12207).

Workflow, n – the sequence of tasks and activities that are carried out to complete a process.

DISCUSSION— A workflow shows the flow of work from one step to the next, including decision points and dependencies. Workflows help visualize how tasks are interconnected and how information moves through the process

The main purpose of the DYNAPORT project is to improve the processes associated with the visit of a ship to a port. Within this context DYNAPORT aims to further refine and improve the sub-process of Just-in-Time (JIT) Arrival. Consequently, we will first start with terms and definitions related to the high-level process.

3.2 Parties and roles

Party, n – A natural person, a team, organisation or organisation part that takes part in an activity, process or transaction.

DISCUSSION—: A “Party” may take on a different “Role” (see separate definition) depending on the context of the activity, process or transaction. In the documentation related to the DYNAPORT project, we will refer to the party by their specific role in the specific context. The same Party may play multiple Roles within the same context (process, activity or transaction)

Role, n - A specific function that is performed by a specific party or combination of parties.

DISCUSSION— The specific function may involve one or multiple related responsibilities. A role may be performed one or a group of parties. However, a specific responsibility always belongs

to a single role. Reference ARKTRANS Chapter 5⁴

This means that a specific role may be performed by different types of parties in different ports or in different types of trade.

Legal Entity, n—Any business, government body, department, charity, individual, or institution that has standing in the eyes of the law and has the capacity to enter into agreements or contracts. Reference [29].

Organisation, n – a group of people who work together in an organized way for a shared purpose. Reference [Cambridge Dictionary](#).

DISCUSSION— In general, an organisation is also a “Legal Entity” (or “Legal Person”) that can enter into legally binding commitments with natural persons or other legal entities.

Natural person, n – A living human being, with certain rights and responsibilities under the law. Reference [Legal Dictionary online](#).

DISCUSSION— By contrast, a “legal person,” or an “artificial person,” is a group of people that is considered by law to be acting as a single individual. Both natural and legal persons are entitled to sue other parties and sign contracts. The captain, crew and passengers aboard a ship are examples of natural person. Natural persons may act on their own behalf or on behalf of an organisation that has authorised them to do so.

3.3 Locations

Location, n – a particular place or position⁵.

DISCUSSION— The term “Location” covers a very wide range of more specific but essentially different concepts. Below are two main categories of such essentially different concepts (Physical versus Digital). Within each of these categories further sub-categories can be distinguished. Each of which is itself essentially different from the others.

The IHO defines a location as “a generic feature that defines and attributes a point in space”, which is very much in line with the definition above.

Geofence, n - a virtual "perimeter" or "fence" around a given geographic feature (a physical location)⁶.

DISCUSSION— A geofence can be dynamically generated (as in a radius around a point location) or match a predefined set of boundaries (such as ports, terminals, warehouses, waiting areas, depots, yards, etcetera). Particular actions may be triggered when an object is detected entering the designated area. This “detection” may take many forms including but not limited to an electronic device communicating its geographic position sending a position located within the geofence boundaries.

⁴ <https://sintef.brage.unit.no/sintef-xmlui/bitstream/handle/11250/2389176/SINTEF%2bA12001.pdf#page=41>

⁵ Reference [Cambridge Dictionary online](#).

⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Geofence>

3.4 Events, status and milestones

Event, n – a significant occurrence that may have an effect on the status/condition of an object. Reference [50]

DISCUSSION—An event may be significant to a single party or multiple parties. Within the DYNAPORT context, the focus will be on the exchange of events that are significant for multiple parties.

Status, n – the distinct condition of an object or a process at a particular time, specifically within the context of the Goods Movement Process. Reference [50]

DISCUSSION— The status may be the result of one or several events having occurred and this status is assumed to persist for a period of time. Reference [50]

Milestone, n – a status that is important to multiple parties and from which a process cannot go back. Reference [50]

DISCUSSION— Milestone may be mutually agreed between parties or based upon standards agreed by industry. A milestone, once achieved, will persist indefinitely. Reference [50]

3.5 Identification

Identifier, n – a name, series of numbers, etc. that is used in a system to represent someone or something⁷.

DISCUSSION— The things and people that may be represented by an identifier can be categorised along two criteria: “Subject versus Object” and “Tangible versus Intangible”. Subjects (e.g., a natural person or an “egal entity”) can be parties on legally binding contracts, whereas Objects (e.g., locations, devices, software) cannot.

Tangible in this context means that the Subject or Object has physical properties (e.g., mass and dimensions); think of a natural person, a ship, a Ship-to-Shore crane or a physical (IT) device. Intangible applies to all other “things” such as an organisation, a set of data (records) or a process⁸.

An identifier merely *represents* the thing or the person associated with the identifier. The below quote from the UN/CEFACT White Paper “*Globally Unique Identifiers in Supply Chains Discoverable, Resolvable, Verifiable*” is very relevant in this context.

“Despite ever advancing technologies which can facilitate electronic data exchange, most trade data is still conveyed on paper (i.e. PDF). One commonly accepted objective of trade digitalization is to entirely remove the use of paper and paper substitutes.

Here the objective is to exchange trade data entirely as structured data.

⁷ IDENTIFIER | English meaning - Cambridge Dictionary;
<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/identifier>

⁸ Based on a White Paper “*Globally Unique Identifiers in Supply Chains Discoverable, Resolvable, Verifiable*” to be published by UN/CEFACT

In principle, the exchange may be limited to identifiers only.

... trade and transport ecosystem ... participants could use identifiers to request information and only receive the information that they need [on demand].

The quote above refers to “trade” domain, but the claim is equally relevant for the “transport” domain⁹.

To move towards the goal stated in ***bold italic***, a number of additional requirements may be placed on the identifiers¹⁰.

- An identifier must be “**discoverable, adj**”, meaning that it can be found and read/interpreted in an automated and technical manner. Relying purely on a human to find and read it is insufficient for meeting the “discoverability” requirement. Automatic Identification and Data Capture (AIDC) technologies such as barcodes, RFID-tags and IoT devices are often used on Tangible Objects for this purpose. Structured information exchanges (based on standards) always meet this requirement.
- An identifier must be “**resolvable, adj**”, meaning that the identifier may be used by authorised parties to access the data associated with the identifier (where ever that data may reside). A key element of this requirement is that the party who has the identifier can easily find out where to access the data. It must refer to a single “thing”; if not, a party using the identifier may find and use data that is **not** associated with the thing the party is interested in. This implies that an identifier must be globally unique if it is to be used in an environment involving many stakeholders that are geographically widely (even globally) dispersed
- An identifier may be “**verifiable, adj**”, meaning the true identity of the controller of an identifier can be determined, which will enable to check the authenticity of the data linked to the identifier. This may include technologies that ensure that any tampering with the data between its origin and the receiver can be detected, but it does not have to.

From the above, it follows that identifiers may be used to find and access (Pull) data/information “on demand” (Linked Data approaches). Such “Pull” approaches may well reduce the volume of data that may need to be transmitted over “limited bandwidth” communication channels.

⁹ UN/CEFACT categorises its system of standards in two main domains “trade” and “transport”

¹⁰ Bullets based on the UN/CEFACT White Paper on Identifiers already mentioned.

4 General Supply Chain, Transport and Logistics terms

All transportation is based on Trade transactions (see definition below) or the anticipation of such transactions. Supply Chain stakeholders need to make sure that the Goods bought/sold in those trade transactions will be relocated from where they are to where they should be.

Transportation would not exist without this need to relocate those goods.

Therefore, we need to establish a basic set of terms and definitions that will enable unambiguous discussions among the stakeholders in Supply Chain and those in Transport & Logistics (T&L) environments.

This section should only include terms and definitions that may be used in multiple modes of transport or for multiple different kinds of goods/cargo, but which are commonly used also in ship related transportation.

Some of the terms included here may be considered as “foundational” for terms that are defined in other sections of this document.

Trade Transaction, n – an instance of the interaction between parties involving the buying and selling of goods or services for mutually beneficial purposes.

DISCUSSION— A “trade transaction” is often also referred to as “Buy/Sell transaction”.
Definition based on [Investopedia](#).

Seller, n – A party who offers goods for sale to other parties.

DISCUSSION— The party may be stipulated on a Sales Order as the party who sold the goods.
Reference ASTM work not yet published.

Buyer, n -A party who purchases goods from other parties.

DISCUSSION— The party may be stipulated on a Sales Order as the party to whom goods have been sold. Reference ASTM work not yet published.

Goods Movement Process (GMP), n - the process of managing and executing transportation generally as a result of a buy-sell transaction for goods between a seller and a buyer. Reference [\[50\]](#).

DISCUSSION— This also includes movement of goods in trade that are not part of the direct sales (e.g. inventory relocation) as well as movement of transport equipment and devices (e.g., racks, tie-downs, pallets, bins, etc.) related to transportation of goods or in anticipation of future transport needs (e.g., positioning and repositioning of containers, chassis or other transportation assets). Reference [\[50\]](#).

Journey (of goods/items), n - A set of consecutive transport movements and other logistics activities needed to move the goods or items from the seller’s facility to the buyer’s (recipient) facility as specified in the Sales Order (Trade transaction)

Transport movement, n - The conveyance (physical carriage) of people, goods, or other objects from place to place. Reference [\[53\]](#)

Transportation hub, n - A place of any size where cargo or goods are exchanged between vehicles and/or between modes of transport.

Transport unit, n - A unit containing a single product, product package, or collection of product or product packages (same or different) designed to enable these to be handled as a single transport entity. (based on ISO/IEC 17360)

DISCUSSION— The "units" may be tangible and physically discrete (e.g., pallets or containers) or they may be "logical" in nature (e.g., in the context of wet bulk several different "parcels" may be identified / distinguished even though they are transported in the same tank / hold).

Reference [\[50\]](#). UN/CEFACT refers to this as a “Goods Item” and GS1 uses the term “Logistic Unit”.

Goods, n - A transport unit or a grouping of transport units assembled and identified by the seller (sender) of the goods traveling under one dispatch to one buyer (recipient). Reference [\[50\]](#).

DISCUSSION— Goods are related to trade transactions. The identification of goods generally occurs at a much more granular/precise level than the HS/HTS codes currently used in Customs and cross-border procedures.

Cargo, n - A transport unit or a grouping of transport units assembled to be transported under one or more transport contracts. Reference [\[50\]](#).

DISCUSSION— Cargo encompasses many more things next to goods such as transport equipment (e.g., containers, racks) and packaging materials (e.g., dunnage, lashings) etcetera. Customs and cross-border procedures tend to focus on the cargo crossing the border.

Shipment, n - an identifiable collection of one or more goods to be transported from the seller to the buyer. Reference [\[50\]](#).

DISCUSSION—A shipment may be executed using multiple consignments. Based on definitions of GS1 and UN/CEFACT.

Consignment, n - an identifiable collection of transport units transported from one consignor to one consignee via one or more modes of transport as specified in one contract. Reference [\[50\]](#).

DISCUSSION— In the case of international movement of cargo as transport units, numerous consignments will occur. International consignments will have a pre-carriage, main carriage and an onward (or post) carriage to manage the movement of cargo to its delivery destination. Based on definitions of GS1 and UN/CEFACT.

Vehicle, n - Any device/means used in any mode of transport that may be used to transport cargo, goods or people.

DISCUSSION—A vehicle may be powered by its own engine or it may have no means to propel itself. Vehicles may be operated by people (even remotely) or operate autonomously. The terms “Vehicle”, “Means of Transport”, “Transport Means” are generally used interchangeably.

Means of Transport, n (Transport Means, n) - The particular vehicle used for the transport of goods or persons.

DISCUSSION—Examples include trucks, cars, (electric) bicycles, ships, aircraft etcetera. Within the DYNAPORT context, we will use the term “Ship” to refer to the “means of transport”

used for the maritime “mode of transport”.

Reference [51]

Transport Equipment, n – a piece of high-value equipment used to hold, protect or secure cargo for transportation purposes.

DISCUSSION— Transport equipment as defined in this document excludes reusable secondary packaging and reusable load carriers, these are called Returnable Transport Items (RTI).

Reference GS1: https://www.gs1.org/docs/tl/T_L_Keys_Implementation_Guideline.pdf

Mode of Transport, n – The method of transport used for the conveyance of goods or persons.

DISCUSSION—Examples include air, rail, road, maritime and inland waterways.

Reference [51]

Service Provider, n - A party offering services to other parties.

DISCUSSION—The services may be provided for a fee or free of charge. A service provider may provide a highly specialized service, a few specific services or very wide portfolio of services.

Logistic Service Provider, LSP, n – A party offering services related to planning and execution of logistic activities.

DISCUSSION- Logistic Service Provider is often abbreviated to LSP. Examples of these services include transportation, warehousing, inventory management, order fulfilment, distribution and supply chain management. Parties offering services covering the financial settlement related to the logistic activities are not considered to be a logistic service provider because their primary line of business is finance and not logistics.

Carrier, n – A logistic service provider undertaking the transport of cargo from one point to another by any means of transport.

DISCUSSION- Examples of parties include natural persons, governments and legal entities such as organizations, associations. In the maritime mode of transport, the carrier is often also referred to by the term “shipping company”.

Owner (of the Cargo), n – The party who owns or has a significant interest in the cargo being transported.

DISCUSSION— This is also often referred to as the Beneficial Cargo Owner. The BCO is usually the Seller or the Buyer of the cargo being transported.

5 Ship voyage related terms

This section will define terms related to ship voyages and movements.

Port call, n – the arrival and departure of a vessel at a particular port as part of its voyage. During a single port call, the vessel may call at one or multiple terminals.

DISCUSSION— The term port call is not always immediately understood outside the maritime community. To facilitate the interaction with other stakeholders, the terms “port visit” and terms derived from “visit” are used widely across supply chains; DYNAPORT will also use those alternate terms in its deliverables and documentation.

Voyage, n - This is a continuous sequence of ship movements, port calls and other ship operations as defined by the voyage planner.

DISCUSSION — A “voyage“ may include repositioning from a previous port, anchorage or other position to the commencement of the first laden passage. A voyage may consist of several passages and will have a structure that is dependent on the type of trade: A short sea feeder may see a voyage as a full roundtrip from the main port, via all smaller ports, and back again to the main port, while a liner operation may see each passage as a voyage.

Note: The term "voyage" has different meaning in different documents from e.g. IMO, IHO and others. It is often used in the same meaning as "passage"

Passage, n - The movement of a ship from one berth to the next berth.

DISCUSSION—The master is responsible for safe planning of the passage by dividing it into several legs, each with a specific operational mode, e.g. speed and heading [13]. The starting berth and the next berth may be in different ports or they may be in the same port. In some cases, the first or next berth may be replaced by an anchorage, a position for ship-to-ship transfer or other positions that are used as start or end of a voyage.

Note: In IEC 63173-1 [41], the term "route plan" is used as something close to a passage as defined here.

Port Passage, n - This is the part of a “passage” where all movements of the ship are with a specific port area.

DISCUSSION— Typically, a “passage” will start in one port and terminate in another. Such a “passage” will also include two “port passages”, one for each of the ports. See also Figure 1 below.

In case a ship visits more than one berth in the port, all of the movements within the port area are considered port passages. The movements between two berths within the same port may be planned separately. If so, each of these will be considered its own port passage (plan).

Sea Passage, n - This is a part of a “passage” where all movements of the ship are in open and unrestricted sea areas.

DISCUSSION — A sea passage is a sequence of legs through which the ship can sail at its normal operating speed. This excludes passages in restricted or controlled seaways like channels, rivers, canals or ports. A sea passage starts with the waypoint FAOP and ends at EO SP (see entries below).

Waypoint, n - Start or end point of a leg”.

DISCUSSION— Within the DYNAPORT context, waypoints are used to distinguish between significantly different parts of movements related to ships.

Note: IHO defines waypoint as “*In ECDIS, in conjunction with route planning, a geographical location (e.g. latitude and longitude) indicating a significant event on a vessel’s planned route (e.g. course alteration point, calling in point, etc.)* [10]

Full away on passage (FAOP), n - This is the waypoint where the ship starts on a sea passage.

DISCUSSION — This waypoint defines the position where the ship may proceed at its contractual speed.

End of sea passage (EOSP), n - This is the waypoint where the ship ends its sea passage.

DISCUSSION — This waypoint defines the position where the ship may slow down to start the port approach or to pick up a pilot.

Leg, n - This is a part of a passage between two waypoints, where the ship sails with approximately the same speed and heading.

DISCUSSION — Even in open unrestricted waters, the heading and speed will normally get minor adjustments through a leg to ensure that the ship meets the destination waypoint. The division of a passage into legs is part of the passage planning that the master must execute or approve [13]. If major adjustments of speed or heading are required within a planned leg, normally due to an unexpected situation, this will usually be seen as an exception involving this and possibly following legs. A part of a passage that would normally be seen as one leg may also be divided into two or more legs if that part of the passage has intermediate reporting points (see “Waypoint”).

In restricted waters (such as in channels, straits and port areas) the variations in heading and speed may be wider than in open water due to the needs of safe navigation in those waters. Nevertheless, the movement between two waypoints identified for navigation through these restricted waters are still considered legs in the DYNAPORT project context.

Port arrival point (PAP), n – A point agreed between ship and port to which port arrival times (estimated, requested, planned or actual) refer.

DISCUSSION – This can be different positions, dependent on the port. Common references are EOSP, pilot pick-up point, or at the point where the ship can be declared an arrived ship according to a charter contract, i.e. usually when entering the fiscal or geographical limits of the port.

Figure 1 Relationships between voyage related terms. Figure 1 below illustrates the main relationships between voyage related terms. The figure merely indicates the sequence within which the various concepts occur in a typical voyage.

The dimensions of the “boxes” below in no way represent the dimensions of the “things” they refer to in reality. E.g., a waypoint by definition has no dimensions at all.

Figure 1 Relationships between voyage related terms.

Note 1: During the sea passage of a voyage the ship may pass through restricted waters (e.g., Suez or Panama Canal, Malacca Strait). In that case, two of the waypoints indicated in Figure 1 will be the EOSP and FASP related to the movement through the restricted waters. In effect, this means the ships passage between two ports includes two sea passages separated by the movement through the restricted waters. The movement through the restricted waters may itself consist of multiple legs separated by waypoints.

Note 2: A voyage may start in open waters. In that case, the boxes for <Departure port> and <Port passage> at the start of the voyage line above do not apply.

Note 3: Ship-to-ship transfer may occur in open unrestricted waters as part of what is considered the sea passage. During these transfers, the ships will follow the same heading and speed. That means that the navigation during the transfer will be considered a leg in the DYNAPORT context. The speed during transfer will be different from the speed maintained in the other legs of the sea passage. The ship-to-ship transfer leg will be separated from the leg preceding and the leg following using waypoints, just like any other leg is.

Vessel Traffic Service (VTS) - A process to monitor and manage ship traffic in busy or sensitive areas to ensure safe and efficient navigation aligned with applicable regulation.

DISCUSSION— VTS activities will vary based on laws and other regulations that apply in the country or locality concerned. These VTS may provide information, advice, and assistance to vessels to prevent collisions, groundings, and other maritime accidents. VTS centres They rely on shore-based systems such as radar, AIS (Automatic Identification System), VHF radio, and other technologies to track vessel movements and communicate with ship crews.

VTS is crucial in areas with high traffic density, narrow waterways, or challenging navigational conditions. They help coordinate vessel movements, provide real-time updates on traffic and weather conditions, and assist in emergency situations.

Reference route, n – The entry to or departure from a port can be communicated as a reference route with relevant route information.

DISCUSSION – A reference route will generally be “constructed” using identifiers for relevant waypoints in the route, as defined in IEC 63173-1 [41]. The movements in between the waypoints are considered legs in the DYNAPORT context. The reference routes are defined by the port independent of a specific ship calling on the port at a specific date and time. The ship will generally take the reference route as the basis for planning its port passage to or from the berth.

5.1 Identifiers for voyage related terms

The terms that refer to a physical location (e.g., all waypoints) may be referenced in the same ways as described in the “Locations” chapter, preferably with identifiers that are discoverable and resolvable.

There are currently no standards for referring to a Voyage, Passage, Sea Passage, Port Passage or Leg. Within the context of “Port Collaborative Decision Making” (PortCDM) and “Sea Traffic Management” proposals have been made for a standard for Voyage identifiers, but those proposals have not been implemented widely.

6 Port-to-Port process

The DYNAPORT deliverables for the “*JIT Arrival process blueprint*” and “*Nautical Voyage Planning*” provide far more detailed information and visuals related to the terms and definitions provided in this document. Since the terms defined here are also used beyond the scope of those specific deliverables, it is important to include them here (at a higher less detailed level).

Process blueprint, n – the set of files and other artefacts that aims to provide sufficient detail and clarity to the user such that different users will be able to implement the process described in the blueprint in a consistent and interoperable fashion.

Port Call Process = Port Call management ???, n - The process to manage the full life cycle of a Port Call.

DISCUSSION— The port call life cycle goes through a number of stages that includes Planning, Execution and Settlement. Within the DYNAPORT context, the focus is on Planning and Execution stages.

Local nautical operations (LNO), v - The processes that enables ships calling on a port to safely navigate into, within and out of the port area.

DISCUSSION— The process already starts potentially a significant distance away from the port (especially in case of JIT Arrival). This process relies on (near) real-time communications among ships as well as among ship and landside services and infrastructure. Today, this is mostly via VHF radio.

Voyage Planning , (NVP) v – The process that helps optimise ship routes, maintain crew safety, and coordinate traffic in and out of (busy) ports and harbours.

DISCUSSION— The process relies heavily on communications among the ship and shore-side services and IT systems.

Ship management services (SMS), v – The processes that support the operation of the ship itself.

DISCUSSION— These processes include the creation and exchanges of voyage orders and reports, technical and maintenance management of the ship, crew management etcetera. The processes are in principle independent of a specific voyage; however, the specific activities within a given process may depend on the requirements of a specific voyage

Port call management (PCM), v - The process that supports the planning and execution of a port call.

DISCUSSION— This may include mandatory reporting to authorities, clearance into ports and terminals, local service planning etcetera.

Port call coordination, n - The process to coordinate all activities in the port related to the planning and execution of Just-in-Time arrival of all vessels calling on the port.

Local port operations (LPO),v – The process that enables the ship to interact with services and infrastructure inside the port.

DISCUSSION— This process is focussed on the activities and services that occur within the immediate port area such as tug services, pilot services, mooring services, land supplied electric power (e.g. "cold-ironing") or cargo handling.

The abbreviations in parenthesis will be used throughout this document as well as in various other DYNAPORT documents and deliverables.

Berth assignment, n – a process in which the ship calling on the port is assigned a specific berth at a specific terminal during a specific period.

DISCUSSION— The process involves a range of checks, including berth-ship compatibility. These checks help to ensure “safe berth-to-berth navigation” as well as safe and smooth cargo operations.

Port entry clearance, n – a process/activity or do we mean this as a status or event related to the vessel. We would need separate definitions for each.

6.1 Identifiers for port processes

In the discussions with port call optimization groups, it would seem that the only necessary reference is the berth call reference. This can be used by the port planner in the coordination of the entire port call process. Because each berth call is always linked to one specific port call, a common identifier for the berth call would suffice for message exchanges among parties involved in the Port Call process.

Local software systems (such as Port Community Systems) may still need a reference code associated with the Port Call to manage the relationships with the various berth calls associated with the Port Call and to be able to unambiguously distinguish between different Port Calls.

7 Parties related to port calls

There are many stakeholders somehow related to the processes of Port Call and JIT Arrival. In this section we provide terms and definitions that described their involvement in those processes and the various interactions occurring within those processes.

We will distinguish between parties and roles. Within the process descriptions roles will be used to keep those descriptions easy to understand and applicable in as many maritime and ports environments as feasible.

Roles in processes are performed by a party (or combination of parties). Exactly who that party is (or parties are) in a specific maritime or ports environment may be different in each specific environment, but the process description using the roles remains essentially the same.

Port Authority, n - The entity responsible for administration and maintenance of harbour facilities. Reference [10] element 3982.

Harbour Master, n - an official responsible for enforcing the regulations of a particular harbour or port, in order to ensure the safety of navigation, the security of the harbour and the correct operation of the port facilities.

Shipping Company, n - A carrier whose line of business is ownership and/or operation of ships.

DISCUSSION- In the maritime mode of transport, “shipping” line is often also referred to by the term “shipping company”.

Terminal Operator, MTO, n – A party engaged in the business of running a maritime Terminal.

DISCUSSION— The term is often abbreviated to MTO. MTOs include: Public port authorities that own and maintain the docks and other facilities, and sometimes directly operate the marine terminal that ocean common carriers use, and Private terminal operators that lease terminals from a public port authority (which acts as a landlord) and operate the leased terminals as a private business.

7.1 Identification of Parties.

There is a plethora of schemes for the identification of parties in use. Most of those are intended for local or even internal use; many are intended for wider shared use (e.g., national, regional or even worldwide). This “abundance” is causing no end of issues and challenges in Supply Chain and Transport & Logistics operations. As mentioned above, current work in UN/CEFACT is looking into how the use of Digital Identifiers may be used to support operations so they may run more effectively and more efficiently. The UN/CEFACT work focusses on identifiers that are intended for widely shared use.

Within the DYNAPORT context, we will “match” the UN/CEFACT work with the identification schemes (and systems) currently used within the scope of the DYNAPORT context with the aim to identify how the identification of parties in the maritime and ports industry may be improved. That improvement will then also enable (massive) improvements in foundational (IT) processes such as authentication and authorisation, without which a smooth exchange of reliable information among parties cannot be achieved.

Table 2 below provides an initial indication of which reference codes and identifiers are or may be used for the various parties mentioned above.

Table 2 – Party identifiers and reference codes

Party	Identifier	Remarks
Port Authority	IMO Company Code Legal Entity Identifier Business Registration GS1 GLN (*)	“Port of Rotterdam (Havenbedrijf Rotterdam NV)” has IMO Company Number “0909773” LEI code “724500JSY5LM1CGP1114” Dutch Chamber of Commerce number “24354561” Global Location Number “8719331162654”
Harbour Master	GS1 GLN (*)	Assuming the Harbour Master’s office is also a legal entity. In small ports, the role of Harbour Master may be performed by a natural person. In those cases, there is no standard identifier available.
Shipping Company	IMO Company Code Legal Entity Identifier Business Registration GS1 GLN	IMO Company Number “0152944” is assigned to Mediterranean Shipping Company SA; (MSC) LEI Code “529900YG6KSURDN8CJ29” Swiss Commercial Register Number “CHE111954803”
Terminal Operator	IMO Company Code Legal Entity Identifier Business Registration GS1 GLN	IMO Company Number “5278330” is assigned to DP World FZE registered in United Arab Emirates LEI Code 98450048FA14HCQCA730 Business registration number “37851485”

(*) GLN = Global Location Number. It is a globally unique identifier that may be used for any organisation of any type and size anywhere worldwide.

8 Roles related to port calls

Hydrographic service provider, HSP, n - The role assigned to a party who undertakes to arrange for the collection and compilation of hydrographic data and the publication, dissemination and keeping up to date of all nautical information necessary for safe navigation [6].

DISCUSSION— Hydrographic service provider is often abbreviated to HSP. Examples of HSP includes National hydrographic office, regional charting agency or the port itself [6].

Performance manager, n – The role assigned to a party who receives performance reports from the ship.

DISCUSSION— The performance manager/s may be a charterer, an MRV verification party [8] or the ship owner in conjunction with the IMO data collection requirements [12] or combination thereof. The performance manager may receive multiple performance reports from the ship also from multiple voyages. The performance manager can then analyse the ship’s performance over time and also across voyages or charter parties (contracts).

Nautical service provider, (NSP), n - The role assigned to a party who provides services related to the safe passage and berthing of the vessel.

DISCUSSION—For example, but not limited to: Pilots, tugs, linesmen, boatmen, or VTS [6].

Ship service provider, (SSP), n - The role assigned to a party who provides services to the ship.

DISCUSSION— The services rendered to the ship include but are not limited to bunkers, lube oil, potable water, provisions, stores, waste per IMO/MARPOL Class, repairs, cargo handling, cargo lashing, terminal operator, cargo survey [6].

This role corresponds to the combined roles of cargo service and vessel service providers in which is named vessel or cargo service provider as per reference [6].

Nautical Traffic Manager, n - The role assigned to a party responsible for the overseeing and sometimes control of maritime traffic.

DISCUSSION— This is often a VTS organisation, although at least the coastal VTS normally does not manage traffic, or it can be other parties who receive information about a ship's planned or ongoing voyage to be used to improve maritime safety, e.g. by utilizing the new ECDIS performance requirements to send or receive routes in S-421 format.

Voyage Planner, n - The role assigned to a party who plans a voyage, including berth calls, cargo loading and discharge.

DISCUSSION— This is often the charterer but may also be the owner in the case of liner shipping.

Passage Optimizer, n - The role assigned to a party or group of parties involved in passage optimization.

DISCUSSION— This optimization includes, but is not limited to, weather routing or other forms of speed and route optimization. Optimization will normally be done only on the open sea part of the passage.

Berth planner, n - The role assigned to a party who plans the berth call.

DISCUSSION- For example, but not limited to maritime terminal operator, berth operator, Port Authority or VTS [6].

Port planner, n - The role assigned to a party who is responsible for planning and coordinating the port call.

DISCUSSION- For example, but not limited to: port authority, harbour master, maritime terminal operator, VTS, pilots, coast guard [6].

Authority, n - The role assigned to a party who receives information related to the port call or provides clearance to the ship's arrival and departure [6].

DISCUSSION- The role may be performed by for example, but not limited to: Harbour Master, customs, immigration, port health, coastguard [6].

Port call coordinator, n - The role assigned to the party managing the arrival coordination process across all ships calling on the port.

DISCUSSION- The role may be performed by for example, but not limited to: port authority or harbour master. The port call coordinator role tends to focus on the interaction with the ship while still underway to the port, whereas the port planner tends to focus more on the period and

activities when the ship is within the port area. The coordination covers both ships following the Just-in-Time approach and those not using it.

The role is also referred to as Port Call Coordinator Centre or **P3C** when it is regarded as a “location” or an “IT-system”.

Figure 2 The Port Call Coordination Centre - Identification of key stakeholders

Table 3 below shows various role definitions from a number of referenced documents. The left most column is the role name assigned in the context of DYNAPORT.

Table 3 - Mapping Roles across industry initiatives

DYNAPORT	FAL.5/Circ.52[6]
Ship operator	Ship operator, ship manager or ship charterer
Voyage planner	Ship operator, ship manager or ship charterer
Ship representative	Ship operator, ship manager, ship charterer or agent
Hydrographic service provider (HSP)	Hydrographic service provider
The ship	New
Passage optimizer	New
Performance manager	New
Nautical traffic manager (NTM)	New

8.1 Identification of Roles related to the Port Call.

Every role is performed by one or a combination of parties. Several standards development organisations (SDO) have code-lists aimed to provide a common understanding of what role an organisation performs within a given context (e.g., a process or a transaction). E.g., GS1 maintains the “OrganisationRoleType” code list for that purpose.

However, those code-lists do **not** identify the exact party who is playing that role. Therefore, IT-systems tend to include attributes in records associated with the roles that need to be recorded and tracked in a specific context. For each of the relevant roles in that context, the system will include a specific identifier to unambiguously refer to a specific party. Any of the identifiers mentioned above for parties may be used also in those role-related attributes.

9 Parties related to the ship and its representatives

As indicated in **Error! Reference source not found.**, the ship may be viewed as the central the port call process (and even the maritime transport process in general). That is also the perspective taken in this document. However, the ship can be represented by several parties as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – The most common ship representatives

The background boxes represent the jurisdictions the parties operate in and are, from left to right:

- **National parties, n** - Parties operating under the same jurisdiction as the port the ship visits, and who are entitled to represent the ship in legally binding ways towards third parties.

DISCUSSION— Most ships will use a local agent in foreign ports to simplify commercial and administrative operations in port.

- **The Ship, n**- The ship acting as a legal entity.

DISCUSSION— The ship may represent itself in legally binding ways towards other parties. This role represents the ship's master, other crew or the ship's information systems in contexts where these entities are responsible for exchange of specific information. Often, the actual exchange of information is performed by other parties such as the ship agent or ship manager on behalf of the ship.

However, it is under the jurisdiction of its flag state. This may limit the freedom to execute certain commercial or administrative operations that are controlled, e.g. under port state jurisdiction. This may make the use of agents necessary in some cases.

- **International parties, n** - Parties not operating under the same jurisdiction as the port the ship visits.

DISCUSSION— The ship owner, ship manager and/or ship charterer is normally giving the voyage orders or instructions to the ship and its captain. These are operating under their respective national jurisdiction, which often is different from flag and port state.

Master, n - The natural person in command of the ship

DISCUSSION— In this document the captain of the ship will be referred to as “master” or “ship master”.

Ship Owner, n – The party that legally owns the ship.

DISCUSSION— The owner may authorise a charterer or a manager to operate the ship.

Ship Charterer, n – The party who hires a ship from a ship owner for a single voyage or a period of time [6].

DISCUSSION— The contract for hire is often called a “charter party”.

Ship Manager, n – The party responsible for the day-to-day management, operation and maintenance of the ship [6].

DISCUSSION— The ship manager may entitle another party to act on his behalf. Examples of those parties include port captain, master of the ship or ship agent. Based on Reference [6]

Ship Agent, n – The party representing the ship's owner and/or charterer in port [6].

DISCUSSION— If so instructed, the agent is responsible to the Principal for arranging, together with the port, a berth, all relevant port and husbandry services, tending to the requirements of the master and crew, clearing the ship with the port and other authorities (including preparation and submission of appropriate documentation) along with releasing or receiving cargo on behalf of the Principal [6].

10 Roles related to the ship and its representatives

Ship representative, n - The party who handles the coordination ship's port call and necessary services to the ship.

DISCUSSION— This may be a proper ship agent as defined in [6], but it can also be the owner, manager or charterer itself. In the latter case, this is either through a local office or through their main offices

Principal, n - Party for whom another party acts as an agent or representative. Reference Oxford Dictionary.

Ship Operator, n - Party that decides how the ship is employed and where a vessel is to call [6].

DISCUSSION— Depending on the commercial operation conditions, for example, but not limited to charterer, shipowner, cargo owner/trader, ship manager, carrier, parties representing/acting on behalf of before mentioned parties [6].

11 Locations

11.1 Geographic features in ports

Many geographic features in the port are used in nautical and operational as well as in administrative processes, tasks and activities that are in scope for the DYNAPORT project. The IHO Hydrographic dictionary {10} identifies a number of these. But first we need to define what a “port” is.

Port, n - Any area, terminal, offshore places and facilities, ship and repair yard, or roadstead which is normally used for the loading, unloading, repair and anchoring of ships, or any other place at which a seagoing ship can call¹¹

DISCUSSION— A ship may call upon a port for many different reasons. In general, different forms of (freight) transport—water, rail and road—converge here. The offshore places include any places outside the legal, fiscal or administrative area of the port, no matter the distance from that area, that are relevant for the planning and execution of the port call including Port Passage Planning areas and places where vessels are ordered to wait for their turn. Any other places and areas needed to facilitate Just-in-Time Arrival processes are explicitly included also.

Note: The IHO dictionary defines the term “port” (element ID 3981) a lot shorter as “A place provided with terminal and transfer facilities for loading and discharging cargo or passengers”.

Port areas

Terminal, n - A number of berths grouped together, providing facilities for handling a particular form of cargo, e.g. oil terminal, container terminal.
Reference {10} element 5383.

DISCUSSION—A terminal is a physical location (facility). Its main function is to allow for the transfer of cargo (e.g., shipping containers) between ships (sea-going and inland waterways) as well as between ships and other modes of transport, such as trucks and trains.

Berth, n - A place where a vessel may moor or anchor.
Reference {10} element 476.

DISCUSSION—Berths are generally associated with a specific terminal.

¹¹ Based on <https://portcalloptimization.org/images/Port%20Information%20Guide%201.1%20-%20clean.pdf> and ASTM F49 efforts not yet published.

Berth position, n - The position along the line of a berth, specified by one point (e.g. bollard, manifold or ramp number), allowing the ship to berth in the correct position along the berth (IMO Data reference model IMO0233). Reference [24] page 25.

Anchorage, n - An area in which vessels anchor or may anchor [10].

DISCUSSION— For the purposes of this document, the identification of a specific anchorage may be required in certain messages [24].

Pilot Boarding Place, n - is a designated location where a maritime pilot boards a vessel to guide it safely through challenging or congested waters, such as harbors, rivers, or straits.

DISCUSSION— It is also referred to as “Pilot Boarding Point”¹².

This place is typically situated at a safe distance from the commencement of the pilotage to ensure safe boarding conditions.

Facility, n - An area within the port that is subject to the International Ship and Port Facility Security (ISPS) Code. Reference Wikipedia.

DISCUSSION— The ISPS code regulations relate to maritime security. In ports, there are also (sometimes many) locations that are not considered “maritime”. Those locations may also be referred to colloquially as a “facility” but within scope of the DYNAPORT project, the term “facility” shall be limited to locations subject to the ISPS Code.

Waiting Area— a collection of locations or berths as designated by the relevant Port Authority for the purpose of becoming an “Arrived Ship” for tendering Notice of Readiness.

DISCUSSION— In general, the area will be indicated as a single contiguous area by the port authority.

Port Passage Planning area, n - the area within which ships receive a Planned Time of Arrival Pilot Boarding Place, based on a Planned Time of Arrival Berth.

DISCUSSION— The time provided may be updated with e.g., but not limited to: weather or tidal conditions, capacity of nautical services, or traffic.

¹² [Pilot boarding point \(imorules.com\)](http://imorules.com)

The figure below provides a conceptual depiction of the port areas and their relation to the concept of the “entire port”.

Figure 4 – Port areas and their relationship to the entire port area

This conceptual figure applies to most ports, but there may be variations in some ports.

11.1.1 Identifiers for geographic features in ports

Table 4 lists some of the locations mentioned above in approximate order of placement in enclosing areas also indicating common identification methods for each of them. Very often, one location may be referred to with more than one identification scheme; the table already indicates this for several of the location types. In most cases currently, local software systems will assign their own unique reference codes for these entities. In fact, sometimes one location may be associated with several dozen different references. Most of those do not meet any of the requirements defined for identifiers mentioned above

Common identifiers for these entities used across software systems (that may be shared in message exchanges) may not be absolutely necessary in all use cases, although using such common identifiers may make management significantly easier also for the local software systems.

Table 4 - Location identification

Feature	Identifier	Remarks
Country	UN Country Code ISO/IEC 3166-1	Highest level in the hierarchy
Port	UN/LOCODE [28] Recommendation 16	Ports tend to use the UN/LOCODE for the “city” that they are located in. (**)
Anchorage	Port specific code	An anchorage is usually referred to by a name that is unique within the port or a port defined code.

Terminal	Port-specific code Trade-specific (e.g., SMDG for containers) GS1 GLN (*)	A terminal can be referred to using a local code, e.g. four letters as indicated in [24]. It can also be an SMDG [32] code, although these are exclusively used by container terminals. A global standard identifier may be used also.
Facility (ISPS)	ISPS code BIC Facility code GS1 GLN (*)	A facility is usually identified by its ISPS facility number from GISIS [33]. This number must be combined with the LOCODE. It may also be identified using a BIC Facility code [31]. A global standard identifier may be used also.
Berth	Port-specific code Trade-specific (e.g., SMDG for containers) GS1 GLN (*)	Generally, identified using a local code or name. It can also be an SMDG [32] code, although these are exclusively used by container terminals. A global standard identifier may be used also.
Berth position	Port-specific code GS1 GLN + extension	Generally identified using a reference to a location along a berth, e.g. distance from start or end, a bollard or a manifold. A global standard identifier may be used also.

(*) GLN = Global Location Number. It is a globally unique identifier that may be used for any location of any type and size anywhere worldwide. It could therefore be used also for the port, anchorage, waiting area or any of the other locations mentioned in this section of the document. Currently however, this is not common practice.

(**) The UN/LOCODE¹³ ((UN Location Code) indicates a geographical area that is (usually) associated with an “administrative” area (according to UN/CEFACT Recommendation 16¹⁴). That means that the UN/LOCODES generally covers an area that is (much) larger than the port facilities themselves.

E.g., NLRTM also covers the Airport of Rotterdam/The Hague, the city of Rotterdam as well as a significant number of suburbs, and terminals/hubs for rail and road transportation among other things. In principle, a UN/LOCODE may identify an area that includes more than one port (but that is a rare occasion).

The UN/LOCODE is also the foundation for a range of other identification schemes that are widely used in the maritime and ports community. ISPS, BIC facility and SMDG codes are so-called “child”-codes of the UN/LOCODE system, meaning that the child-codes are unique only in combination with a specific UN/LOCODE.

E.g., the facility for “Holland Shipyards BV” in Hardinxveld (in The Netherlands) is located within the UN/LOCODE area NLHGS and has “IMO port-facility number” NLHGS-0002.

IMO issues the numerical sequence part (0002), which combined with the UN/LOCODE provides a globally unique reference for the facility. The sequence number part on its own is not unique, because the IMO follows the same approach for every port.

NLRTM-0002 refers to “Barge Center Waalhaven B.V. (55-1)” in Port of Rotterdam.

NLVLI-0002 refers to “Zeeland Refinery” in Port of Vlissingen.

Another issue with UN/LOCODE is that they tend to cover areas on land only, meaning that locations outside the coastline may not be covered by the UN/LOCODE that covers the other

¹³ <https://unece.org/trade/uncefact/unlocode>

¹⁴ <https://unece.org/trade/publications/recommendation-ndeg16-united-nations-code-trade-and-transport-locations>

facilities/locations of the port¹⁵. UN/LOCODES are an “approximate” identifier for a port, which is probably sufficient for most current “manual” processes.

Future digitalised processes may require a more granular and more exact identifier for ports and locations associated with the port (be they on land or on water). Even then, the traditional UN/LOCODES will need to be associated with the more granular identifiers to ensure interoperability of traditional and digitalised processes.

Many geographic features in the port are used both by nautical and operational message exchanges. The Guide for Nautical Data [24] identifies a number of these. All position references can be given in geographic coordinates, as an area, a line or a point, but that is omitted from this discussion. As a general international reference code, two approaches have been suggested:

1. **Global Location Number (GLN):** This is a numeric code maintained by GS1 [29] and is used in international businesses to identify different types of locations. It is also used by some ports to identify relevant geographic features in their ports.
The basic GLN is a 13-digit long number, including a checksum digit.
2. **Maritime Resource Name (MRN):** This is a general coding scheme proposed by IALA and IHO and is a subset of the more general universal resource name (URN).
The MRN is context dependent in that it employs a hierarchical structure to provide the MRN, e.g. urn:mrn:iala:aton:us:1234.5 to provide a code for a specific aids to navigation in the USA. There is a defined mechanism for encoding GLN in an MRN.

Both identification schemes will in principle need a "yellow pages" service to resolve the identifier to the actual geographic location and other attributes that are associated with the location, e.g. function, owner etc. MRN encodes some of these attributes in the MRN itself at the cost of creating a longer and more complex MRN structure. The benefit of having a globally accepted system such as MRN or GLN is mainly to simplify interpretation of different identifiers and to ensure that the same identifier is used in all messages independent of purpose of the message.

12 Events, Statuses and Milestones

Stakeholders in supply chain and transport & logistics often use the terms event, status and milestone without a clear definition of what the terms mean. This is true even for some standards and guidelines developed and maintained by organisations that are well-established or influential in the industry. Furthermore, the definitions used by various sources for the same term are not always well-aligned and sometimes contradictory.

The processes of port call optimization and Just-in-Time Arrival cannot function unless there is a set of terms and definitions that will be commonly used by stakeholders involved in those processes. This chapter covers the essential set of terms and definitions needed to make those processes work well.

¹⁵ There in fact less than 50 UN/Locodes that refer to locations/installations in international waters/ Those all start with the “country code” XZ.

There are four “modifiers” that may be used in combination with the terms “event” and “milestone”:

1. **Actual, adj** - existing in fact or reality¹⁶.
DISCUSSION— In the DYNAPORT context, the modifier “actual” indicates that the event or milestone has in fact occurred.
2. **Estimated, adj** - tentatively or approximately provided¹⁷
DISCUSSION— In the DYNAPORT context, the modifier “estimated” indicates that the event or milestone has yet to occur. It is also accepted by all stakeholders that the estimation provided is likely to change also dependent on the period between the present and the estimated date and time.
3. **Requested, adj** - something asked for¹⁸.
DISCUSSION— In the DYNAPORT context, the modifier “requested” indicates that the event or milestone has yet to occur. It is accepted by all stakeholders that the date and time asked for is the target that the parties involved are aiming for. Nevertheless, requested ate and time may still change also dependent on the period between the present and the requested date and time.
4. **Planned, adj** - having a specific intention¹⁹.
DISCUSSION— In the DYNAPORT context, the modifier “planned” indicates that the event or milestone has yet to occur. It is accepted by all stakeholders that the date and time provided is “firmer” than “estimated” and “requested”. Nevertheless, the planned date and time may still change also dependent on the period between the present and the planned date and time.

The ISO/IEC standards 19987 and 19988 (references [54] and [55]) cover the exchanges of information related to events amongst multiple systems that may be operated by multiple parties. The content of this section is largely based on those standards.

Each event has at least the following main characteristics:

1. It relates to an object (tangible or intangible) that can be identified unambiguously.
answers WHAT object is concerned?
2. It is associated with an unambiguous date (and time).
answers WHEN?
3. It occurs in an unambiguously identifiable place.
answers WHERE?
4. It includes an indication of what occurred that is significant to the interested parties in a way/s that are commonly understood.
answers WHY?

¹⁶ Based on <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/actual>

¹⁷ Based on <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/estimated>

¹⁸ Based on <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/requested>

¹⁹ Based on <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/planned>

Other information may be associated with an event also (e.g., related to the condition of the object or the environment of the object).

Within the DYNAPORT context, all events exchanged will include the four characteristics mentioned above in line with the ISO/IEC standards. Some events will also include additional information; here too the additional information will be aligned with the ISO/IEC standards to the extent feasible.

The processes within scope of the DYNAPORT project rely on a variety of timestamps (WHEN) related to a movement or an activity (a service). For the movement events, one needs to know whether it is an **arrival** at a specified location or a **departure** from a specified location. For the activities or services, one needs to know whether those were **started** or **completed**.

The table below represents the combination of the modifiers for events mentioned above with the concepts of arrival, departure, start and completion.

Abbreviation	Definition in FAL.5/Circ.52[6]
ETA, RTA, PTA, ATA	Time of arrival
ETD, RTD, PTD, ATD	Time of departure
ETS, RTS, PTS, ATS	Time of start (e.g. of some service to the ship)
ETC, RTC, PTC, ATC	Time of completion (e.g. of some service to the ship)

E = Estimated, R = Requested, P = Planned, A = Actual

The above table already shows that the WHEN- and WHY-part of an event can be logically constructed from constituent elements: modifier + timestamp + activity.

This idea is in fact extensible for the entire event. We merely need to add the WHAT and the WHERE parts to arrive at “modifier + timestamp + activity + object + location”.

For example:

- Requested Time of Arrival of Ship at Pilot Boarding Place
- Planned Time of Departure of Ship from Pilot Boarding Place
- Actual Time of Start of unloading of Ship at Berth
- Estimated Time of Completion of loading of Ship at Berth

The above examples are ship-oriented. However, the structure of events described in the ISO/IEC standards is applicable to all modes of transport. E.g.,

- Planned Time of Arrival of Truck at Terminal Gate
- Actual Time of Departure of Aircraft from Airport

are valid events as well. When the event names are constructed in this way, they do not really need any further explanation to understand them at a high level.

The ISO/IEC standards also allow for more complex events than described in document, but those are not expected to be applicable within the processes within scope for the DYNAPORT context.

Events related to arrival and departure of ships as well as those related to the start and completion of services/activities require much more detailed definitions of what physical activity related to them is the exact point in time that the arrival, departure, start or completion is deemed to have occurred. In other words, what is the exact “trigger event”.

For instance, the arrival of a ship at berth may be associated with several different events that may occur significant periods apart from each other:

- First line ashore; first mooring cable from the ship on land.
- Last line ashore; final mooring cable from the ship on land.
- All lines fast; all mooring cables from the ship tightened and secured at appropriate mooring devices (such as bollards, mooring dolphins, etcetera).

Especially for large ships (e.g., bulk carriers, extra-large container vessel) several hours may pass between the first line ashore and “all lines fast”.

The maritime and ports industry has not yet agreed standards for those exact trigger events.

The DYNAPORT project will **not** decide on the specific trigger events, but where the industry has defined the exact trigger events, those will also be used within the DYNAPORT project.

In case agreed standard exact trigger events are available they will be included in this section of this document for convenience with reference to the original sources.

The figure below illustrates how modifier, timestamp, activity, object and location combine to become a clearly defined event. The examples provided for activity, object and location are just a few of the full set that may be used in maritime and port operations.

Figure 5 – Visualisation of the components of an Event

13 Contractual and Regulatory terms

Processes covered within the scope of the DYNAPORT project, are to a large extent driven by regulation and “standard” contract clauses that may be mandatory or are widely used by the maritime and ports industry.

These regulation and contract clauses include concepts, terms and definitions that will also have to be used throughout the deliverables and documentation from the DYNAPORT project.

Charter Party, n - a highly standardized written document that provides the contractual arrangements for one party (the charterer) to hire the carrying capacity of a vessel, either in whole or in part, owned by another party²⁰.

DISCUSSION— These contracts outline the rights and obligations of the shipowner and the charterer, ensuring smooth operations during the charter period. These agreements are crucial for facilitating global trade and ensuring that goods and passengers are transported efficiently and safely using the maritime mode of transport. There are basically three types of charter parties:

1. **Time Charter:** The charterer leases the vessel for a specific period and has control over its use, including determining the ports of call and the cargo carried.
2. **Voyage Charter:** The charterer hires the vessel for a single voyage, paying for the transportation of goods from one port to another.
3. **Bareboat Charter:** The charterer leases the vessel without crew or provisions, taking full responsibility for its operation and maintenance during the charter period. The charterer essentially becomes the temporary owner of the vessel.

Arrived Ship, n – “the ship is at the immediate and effective disposition of the charterer at the destination to which it has been ordered” [7]

DISCUSSION— This is the most commonly used definition, but there are some variations based on the exact clauses in the contract (charter party) agreed between the ship owner and ship operator.

Notice of Readiness, NOR, n - The formal notification from the vessel that the vessel is ready in every respect to commence loading or discharging cargo at the agreed-upon port under the applicable charter party²¹.

²⁰ [Charter Parties \(admiraltypractice.com\)](https://www.admiraltypractice.com/charter-parties/)

²¹ Based on [Notice of Readiness \(NOR\) - Definition, Contents & Requirements \(cultofsea.com\)](https://cultofsea.com/notice-of-readiness-nor-definition-contents-requirements/) and [Notice of Readiness \(maritimeoptima.com\)](https://maritimeoptima.com/notice-of-readiness/)

DISCUSSION— The Notice of Readiness is a fundamental component of cargo operations in the shipping industry. It serves as an official record of the vessel's readiness. The NOR is the basis for numerous processes in the shipping industry. For the NOR to be valid at least the following requirements must be met:

- The ship must be at the agreed location
- The ship must be physically and legally ready
- All necessary documentation must be completed.

Laycan, n - The time window within which a ship must arrive at a location.

DISCUSSION— The most common location specified for the laycan is a port. The word “laycan” is combination of the terms "lay days" and "cancellation". The Notice of Readiness must be tendered within the laycan.

Laydays, n - The period within which the shipowner should make the vessel "ready" to the Charterer at the place and time agreed in the charter party.

DISCUSSION— The last day of "Laydays" is called the "Cancelling Date" is, which acts as a deadline to tender "Notice of Readiness". A ship (vessel) failing to become an "Arrived Ship" by tendering a valid Notice of Readiness bears the risk of being refused/cancelled by Charterers as per Charter-Party provisions. Reference Wikipedia

Laytime, n - The contractual maximum time allowed for loading or discharge of cargo after NOR has been tendered

DISCUSSION— The time window the ship has for berth operations will generally be the sum of the laycan and the laytime, with certain contractual variations, e.g. for moving the ship between berths, exclusion of days when stevedores are not working etcetera.

Virtual Arrival, n - The concept whereby a vessel is requested to arrive to a port later than she could reach the port steaming at full speed.

DISCUSSION— The charterer agrees to accept the vessels NOR at the time that the vessel would have arrived at the port had she steamed at full speed but the vessel is allowed to steam at a lower speed, saving fuel, and arriving at the port at a designated time, which will normally be when the port/berth is ready to receive the ship This avoids a port anchorage filling up with ships, reduces collision risks in the anchorage area and reduces emissions in the port area [\[15\]](#)

14 Information and Communications technology

Maritime ICT Reference Architecture, MIRA, n - A standardized overview of parties, roles, ICT systems and communication systems used as a reference for real implementations.

DISCUSSION— The purpose is mainly to define unambiguous terminology for the different concepts as well as relationships between them. This is dependent on having semantic interoperability (as identified in the European Interoperability Framework [1]) for the context of the processes covered in the DYNAPORT project.

Voyage Planning System, ECDIS, n – A system used to plan, monitor, and manage a ship's journey from departure to destination.

DISCUSSION— It involves the preparation of a detailed plan that outlines every aspect of the voyage, including but not limited to route selection, fuel management, cargo planning, and regulatory compliance. The system ensures that the voyage is safe, efficient, and compliant with international maritime regulations. For more detailed and authoritative information, refer to the International Maritime Organization (IMO) [Guidelines for Voyage Planning](#).

Electronic Chart Display Information System, ECDIS, n – A geographic information system used for nautical navigation that complies with International Maritime Organization (IMO) and IHO regulations as a method of electronic navigation.

DISCUSSION— It is considered as an alternative to paper nautical charts for navigation by ships.

Port Management Information System, PMIS, n - The data system used by the port authority to manage ship arrivals and departures in a specific port.

DISCUSSION— In general, this system is used by the port authority. The PMIS may also be used to manage anchorages, berths and other locations and facilities that the port authority has control over. Some nautical services may be managed from the PMIS if the port authorities are in control of these services.

VTS Information System, VTIS, n - The data system that is used to support the Vessel Traffic Services and used by VTS operators to manage ship traffic in and around the port.

DISCUSSION— The system may in some cases be connected to the Maritime Single Window used for the port, but often information is entered by the VTS operators themselves when ships send information to them.

Port Community System, PCS, n - A system that provides a single interface to many or all the previously mentioned systems.

DISCUSSION— The system is usually provided by a third party. The third party may still have (close) connections with parties active in the port. The PCS may also provide other services and functions e.g., related to better connecting hinterland transportation with the maritime ship operations.

The systems mentioned in this chapter and other systems as well as their interactions is further discussed in the MIRA documentation produced in Work Package 5.

Service provider system, n - A system used by a service provider.

DISCUSSION— The system may be used for various purposes, including ship or nautical services. Service Provider systems are used by agents or the ship to manage service bookings.

Maritime Single Window, MSW, n – A system that provides the single point clearance systems for arriving ships.

DISCUSSION— The system is operated by the port state authorities and will handle all authority related reporting in conjunction with a ship call. This system is usually implemented on national or state level for all ports in the country or state.

Terminal Operating Systems, TOS, n: A system with the primary purpose to manage movements and storage of cargo in the terminal.

DISCUSSION— To support their primary purpose, a TOS will often also manage berths and ship departures and arrivals. In the DYNAPORT context, we use the term TOS (terminal operating system) on the assumption they support the latter functions, even in case a separate IT system may be used for those functions. Some nautical services may be managed from the TOS or if the terminals are in control of these services.

References – Standards – etcetera

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Index

- Actual, adj,** 39
- Adjective,** 7
- Agent (of the ship), n,** 32
- Anchorage, n,** 35
- Arrived Ship,** 42
- Authority, n,** 28
- Beneficial Cargo Owner, 19
- Berth assignment, n,** 25
- Berth planner, n,** 28
- Berth position, n,** 35
- Berth, n,** 34
- Buy/Sell transaction, 17
- Buyer, n,** 17
- Cargo, n,** 18
- Carrier, n,** 19
- Charterer (of the ship), n –,** 32
- Consignment, n,** 18
- discoverable, adj,** 16
- Electronic Chart Display Information System, n,** 44
- End of sea passage,** 21
- EOSP,** 21
- Estimated, adj,** 39
- Event,** 15
- Facility (ISPS), n,** 35
- FAOP,** 21
- Full away on passage,** 21
- Geofence, n,** 14
- Goods Item, 18
- Goods Movement Process (GMP), n,** 17
- Goods, n,** 18
- Harbour Master, n,** 26, 28
- Hydrographic service providers, n,** 27
- International parties, n –,** 32
- journey (of goods/items), n,** 17
- Laycan, n,** 43
- Laytime, n,** 43
- Leg, n,** 21
- Legal Entity, n,** 14
- Local nautical operations (LNO),** 24
- Local port operations (LPO),** 25
- Location, n,** 14
- Logistic Service Provider, n,** 19
- Logistic Unit., 18
- Manager (of the ship), n,** 32
- Maritime ICT Reference Architecture, n,** 44
- Maritime Single Window, n,** 45
- Maritime Terminal Operator, n,** 26
- Master (of the ship), n,** 32
- Means of Transport, n,** 18
- Milestone,** 15
- Mode of Transport, n,** 19
- National parties, n,** 31
- Nautical service provider, n,** 27
- Nautical Traffic Manager, n,** 28
- Nautical Voyage Planning (NVP),** 24
- NOR,** 42
- Notice of Readiness,** 42
- Noun,** 7
- NVP,** 24
- Organisation, n,** 14
- Owner (of the Cargo), n,** 19
- Owner (of the ship), n,** 32
- P3C,** 29
- Party, n,** 13
- Passage Optimizer, n,** 28
- Performance manager (Ship), n,** 27
- Pilot Boarding Place, n,** 35
- Pilot Boarding Point, 35
- Planned, adj,** 39
- Port (maritime), n**
- Port Authority, n,** 26, 28
- Port Call, 20,** 24
- Port call coordination, n,** 24
- Port Call Coordinator Centre, n,** 29
- Port call coordinator, n,** 28
- Port call management (PCM),** 24
- Port Call Process,** 24
- Port Community System, n,** 44
- Port entry clearance, n,** 25
- Port Management Information System, n,** 44
- Port Passage Planning area, n,** 35
- Port Passage, n,** 20
- Port planner, n,** 28
- Principal, n,** 33
- Process blueprint,** 24
- Reference route,** 23
- Requested, adj,** 39
- resolvable, adj,** 16

Role, n -, 13
Sea Passage, n, 20
Seller, n -, 17
Service provider system, n, 45
Service Provider, n, 19
Ship, 18
Ship (Legal Entity), n, 31
Ship management services (SMS), 24
Ship Operator, n, 33
Ship Passage, n, 20
Ship service provider, n, 27
Ship Voyage, n, 20
Shipment, n, 18
Shipping Line, n, 26
Status, 15
Terminal (maritime), n, 34
Terminal Operating Systems, n, 45

Trade Transaction, n, 17
Transport Equipment, n, 19
Transport Means, n, 18
transport movement, n, 17
Transport unit, n, 18
transportation hub, n, 17
Vehicle, n, 18
Verb, 7
verifiable, adj, 16
Vessel Traffic Services (VTS), 23
Virtual Arrival, n, 43
Voyage Planner, n, 28
Voyage Planning System, n, 44
VTS Information System, n, 44
Waiting Area (Ship), n, 35
Waypoint (Nautical), n, 21